

International Journal OF Engineering Sciences & Management Research

A STUDY ABOUT EFFECT OF SOCIO ECONOMIC TRENDS ON STUDENTS

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.59832

ABSTRACT

Students are influenced by current socio economic trends. Awareness for quality education, studies in English medium schools, girl's education promotion, participation in activities, advance teaching pedagogy, learning by activities, expense on education, family support are current socio economic trends. These trends influence positively quality education concept.

INTRODUCTION

Students are the beneficial unit of the Quality Education System. The Students are at the focus of QES and are widely affected by the socio economic trends. Students select the field as career which enables them to be the eligible citizen of the world.

The relationship between school resources and student achievement has been controversial, in large part because it calls into question a variety of traditional policy approaches. Students want to move according to current trends, they select career, study, even their attitude expressed according to present social trends. Behavior pattern of students, educators, employees and professionals are moving towards the use of quality tools for learning, working and teaching. The involvement of students is integral to quality system. Student may reject perfectly good and useful concept and services providing a service to specification does not guarantee success. Students have aim to make a brilliant career, follow the path enlighten by educational institute. Students learn best in a style suited to their needs and inclinations. An educational institution that takes the total quality route must take seriously the issue of learning styles and needs to have strategies for individualization and differentiation in learning. Educational institutions have an obligation to make learners aware of the variety of learning methods available to them. They need to get opportunities to learning in a variety of different styles.

METHODOLOGY

Survey report collected from all students of all educational institutes. Student belonging schools, colleges, coaching institutes, designing institutes are included in the study. 160 students up to 11th class, 100 students of 12th class related to 6 schools are taken for study. 25 students from 2 higher education college, 25 students from 2 engineering college, 25 from 2 management college, 25 students from 2 designing institutes, 20 students from 2 medical education centre, 20 students from 2 CA/CS coaching institutes are included for study. Collected data is classified, tabulated and analyzed to find result.

To observe quality aspect trend combine students are divided in 3 groups as participatory concerned for quality education, non participatory but concerned and not concerned. Student response was converted into % and presented in table and chart.

RESULT & ANALYSIS

Table-1: Year wise Criteria for selection of institute by students (%)

S.n.	Year	Concerned for quality education	Concerned for fees	Concerned for infra structure	Concerned for brand name of institute	Concerned for facilities	Concerned for other criteria
1	2009	33	21	19	11	14	2
2	2010	36	20	21	12	8	3
3	2011	38	18	21	11	9	3
4	2012	42	16	22	9	8	3
5	2013	44	17	24	8	5	2

Source: Data collected from students

Chart-1: Year wise Criteria for selection of institute by students (%)

Effect of socio economic trends on students in past 5 years related data shows that awareness for quality education is increased in students. In 2009, 33% students were aware for quality education and in 2013 this awareness reached up to 44%.

Students are concerned for fees also. This criteria percentage is decreased and shows that now students have understood the fact that for quality education fees will be charged. They will have to pay more money for higher level study. On the basis of fees, fewer students are selecting institutes in comparison of past years.

Students are concerned for infrastructure of institute. Increasing % shows that year by year students are expecting good infrastructure of institute. In past, brand name of institute was the reason of success of institutes. In recent years, this trend decreased showing awareness regarding quality management of institute.

Regarding instructional facilities of institute students are now more concerned. From 2009 to 2013, this trend value increased from 5% to 14%. Students are more concerned for facilities. This data indicates that year by year students are becoming quality concerned.

Similarly selection criteria of education institute are related to effect of quality aspects on students. Students choose institute on the basis of fees, brand name, infra structure, available facilities, student result, career assistance etc.

Table-2: Student's Role toward Quality Management

S.N.	Quality Aspects	Participatory Concerned student in (%)	Non Participatory Concerned student in (%)	Not Concerned student in (%)
1	Personality Dev	71	18	11
2	Result	82	6	12
3	Skill Dev	68	15	17
4	Placement	47	24	19
5	Career Dev	77	14	9

6	Physical Fitness	59	23	18
7	Cultural	56	31	13
8	Seminar	64	22	14
9	Moral Value	77	14	9

Source: Data Collected from all education institutes through questionnaire

Chart-2: Student's Role toward Quality Management

Table-3: Criteria of Selection of Education Institute for Study by Students

Concerned For Quality Education	Concerned For Fees	Concerned for Infra Structure	Concerned for Brand Name of Institute	Concerned for Facilities	Concerned for Other Criteria
44	17	24	8	5	2

Source: Data Collected from all education institutes through questionnaire

Chart-3: Criteria of Selection of Education Institute for Study by Students

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Analysis report of quality aspect data shows that students require academic result, personality development, moral value and career development. For personality development quality concerned are 71%, non participatory concerned are 18% and not concerned students are 11%. For academic result 82% students are concerned, 6% are not participatory concerned and 12 % students are not concerned. 68% students showed interest towards skill development and 17% found as not concerned. Placement participatory concerned are 47%, non participative concerned are 24%, non concerned are 19%. In case of career development 77% students are participative concerned, 14% non participative and 9% are not concerned. Student needs physical fitness guidance also. Trends show that 59% are participative concerned, 23% non participative concerned, and 18% are not concerned. For cultural participation 56% students, calculated as participatory concerned, 31% as non participative concerned and 13% not concerned. Seminar participation related views show 64% participatory, 22% non participatory and 14% not concerned. Result regarding moral value indicates that 77% students are participatory concerned, 14% non participatory and only 9% are not concerned. Multi facet development of student is possible through quality education that's why first option of students is quality institute. Effect of quality education is very positive.

Data regarding criteria of selection of institute by student shows that 44% students are concerned for quality and 17% are fees concerned. 8% students select institute because of brand name impression, 5% students are concerned for facilities and 2% students select institute being based on other criteria.

CONCLUSION

Students are positive for quality management institutes as they require best result, best career. They have wish to study in an institute where they may have guidance for academic performance, efficiency development, multi facet personality development. To find this status, questions regarding criteria for selection of institute, effect of quality tools on student, their desire were used. Students want to stand in first row they are curious to know more and more. Present socio economic trends effect positively which supports quality system.

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